

Lepcha

also known as “Rong”

Data source: eHRAF

By Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

Entry tags: Religion, Buddhist Traditions, Indic Religious Traditions, Indic Buddhist Traditions, Modern Buddhist groups, Buddhism of Tibetan origin (Tibetan refugee communities in India, mostly in Bhoutan, Ladakh, Nepal and Sikkim), Scholastic traditions of Mahāyāna in India

The Lepcha live along the southern and eastern slopes of Mount Kanchenjunga in the Himalayas, which is located in the districts of Sikkim and Darjeeling, India. This entry focuses specifically on the Lepchas of Lingthem, a town within Sikkim, India. The Lepchas practice at least two different religions, the older Mun religion (named after the priests), and Mahayana Buddhism (often referred to as Lamaism due to Tibetan influence). While the religions are quite contradictory with each other, they are practiced simultaneously and without animosity. Buddhism was introduced to the Sikkim area in the sixteenth century, and the majority of Lepchas now follow the Buddhist faith. As such, when using the term “religious group” this entry is referring to the Buddhist Lepchas.

Date Range: 1920 CE - 1938 CE

Region: Lingthem and vicinity

Region tags: Asia, South Asia, India

Lingthem, India, and vicinity, ca. 1937

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Murdock and Wilson, 1972. Settlement Patterns and Community Organization: Cross-Cultural Codes 3. *Ethnology*, 11(3), 254-259.
- Source 3: Murdock and Morrow, 1970. Subsistence Economy and Supportive Practices: Cross-Cultural Codes 1. *Ethnology*, 9(3), 302-330.
- Source 1: Tuden and Marshall, 1972. Political Organization: Cross-Cultural Codes 4. *Ethnology*, 11(4), 436-464.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ak05-001>
- Source 1 Description: Gorer, G., & Hutton, J. H. (1938). *Himalayan Village: An Account Of The Lepchas Of*

Sikkim. London: Michael Joseph, Ltd.

– Source 2 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ak05-002>

– Source 2 Description: Morris, J. (1938). *Living With Lepchas: A Book About The Sikkim Himalayas*. London: William Heinemann Ltd.

– Source 3 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ak05-000>

– Source 3 Description: DiMaggio, J. (2003). *Culture Summary: Lepcha*. New Haven, Conn.: HRAF.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "In the last census nearly all Lepchas are entered as Buddhists; a little over a thousand had been converted to Christianity. Despite the small numbers the Lepchas represent one of the most fruitful fields of missionary endeavor in Northern India..." (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:38).

Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: "The discussion of the Lepchas' religion is rendered extremely complicated by the fact that they practise simultaneously, and without any feeling of theoretical discomfort, two (or possibly three) mutually contradictory religions: of these the older Lepcha religion is nameless but, on the analogy of lamaism, I propose calling it the Mun religion (after the title of the priests); the worship of the people of Mayel, which was possibly originally separate, forms nowadays a part of the Mun religion; and this religion is in all its major beliefs opposed to lamaism" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:181).

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1649 indicates that internal warfare seems to be absent or rare, and SCCS Variable 1654 indicates that the society is not pacified for all or part of the twenty-five-year time period (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1650 indicates that external warfare seems to be absent or rare, and SCCS Variable 1654 indicates that the society is not pacified for all or part of the twenty-five-year time period (Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religion have official political support

Answer 'yes' also in cases where the religious and political spheres are not distinguished from one another, but the religious group's activities are tied up with, and supported by, the functioning of the

society at large.

– Yes

Notes: "...the religion of lamaism, which is the official religion of the State [of Sikkim]" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:37). "The Maharajah [ruler of Sikkim] is a fervent Buddhist and gives active encouragement to the lamas [religious leaders]..." (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:42).

Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

Notes: Religious observance is not enforced by the polity, but it is encouraged. "The Maharajah [political leader of Sikkim] is a fervent Buddhist and gives active encouragement to the lamas [religious leaders]" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:42).

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 120

Notes: Because the majority of the population was indicated to be Buddhist (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:38), I estimate that 120 of the 179 inhabitants of Lingthem are Buddhist. "There were altogether thirty-three houses in Lingtem, and a total population of one hundred and seventy-nine souls" (Morris, 1938:24).

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 67

Notes: Because the majority of the population was indicated to be Buddhist (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:38), I estimate that 100 of the 179 inhabitants of Lingthem are Buddhist (67% of the population). "There were altogether thirty-three houses in Lingtem, and a total population of one hundred and seventy-nine souls" (Morris, 1938:24).

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Notes: "The discussion of the Lepchas' religion is rendered extremely complicated by the fact that they practise simultaneously, and without any feeling of theoretical discomfort, two (or possibly three) mutually contradictory religions: of these the older Lepcha religion is nameless but, on the analogy of lamaism, I propose calling it the Mun religion (after the title of the priests); the worship of the people of Mayel, which was possibly originally separate, forms nowadays a part of the Mun religion; and this religion is in all its major beliefs opposed to lamaism" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:181).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "The lamas (to a lesser extent the nuns) are arranged in a disciplined hierarchy. They are a

section of society which performs for the whole society its religious functions; in return the rest of society should give material support to the lamas" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:192).

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

Hierarchy need not be formally institutionalized if it is widely recognized and accepted.

– Yes

Notes: "The lamas (to a lesser extent the nuns) are arranged in a disciplined hierarchy" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:192).

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– Number of levels [numeric value]: 7

Notes: The hierarchy is based on increasing levels of knowledge, not power or control. "Above chapti-bu [the first grade of lamas] there are six grades of lamas; to pass from one grade to another demands firstly increasing knowledge and secondly validating feasts—chaptok klon" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:196).

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: "The higher lamas, the om₂zet and Dorjé Lapoon, perform mystic exercises for the good of their soul and to acquire supernatural powers. These exercises consist firstly in acquiring the requisite instruction and then being immured in a specially prepared and completely dark room called tyang-gong for a certain period" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:212)

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Yes

Notes: After acquiring instruction, the higher lamas must be immured (which entails a strict meditative practice), and perform certain deeds before acquiring supernatural powers (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:212).

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– Yes

Notes: "The higher lamas, the om₂zet and Dorjé Lapoon, perform mystic exercises for the good of their soul and to acquire supernatural powers. These exercises consist firstly in acquiring the requisite instruction and then being immured in a specially prepared and completely dark room called tyang-gong for a certain period" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:212).

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– No

Notes: "The vocation to become a lama is determined by the horoscope which is cast on the third day after birth. All the children of lamas should themselves become lamas, but in practice usually only the eldest son follows the whole career; the younger ones receive

sufficient preliminary instruction to enable them to read one or two sacred manuals. The children of laymen are also occasionally predestined to become lamas, usually because they are reincarnations of dead lamas; should a child so predestined not follow his vocation as a lama he will become a half-wit. It occasionally happens that people who are not predestined to become lamas wish to study; they may do so, but 'their destiny will overcome them'" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:195).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: "Like other religions too, lamaism presents three aspects: a justifying mythology and scriptures, an ethic, and a social organisation" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:189).

Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: "The foundation and justification of lamaism is contained in the scriptures, above all in the two enormous collections of holy writings, the Kangyour or commandments (the Bible) and the Tangyour or commentaries (the Talmud). In these, together with other minor works, are to be found all knowledge and all necessary instruction for the conduct of life" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:189).

Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: The Lamas are specially trained to read and transmit the scriptures.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 66 indicates that "the most impressive structure (or type of structure) is a temple, church, commemorative monument, or other essentially religious or ceremonial edifice" (Murdock and Wilson, 1972).

Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 19

Notes: "The Lingtem monastery is about sixty feet square and has two storeys" (Morris, 1938:19).

- ↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:
 - I don't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "...for the lamas [dreams] are the experiences of the soul released from the body by sleep; unbound by space or time the soul has experiences with the souls of other people, supernaturals and objects, and, on its return, informs the body it inhabits" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:183).

- ↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: "...for the lamas [dreams] are the experiences of the soul released from the body by sleep; unbound by space or time the soul has experiences with the souls of other people, supernaturals and objects, and, on its return, informs the body it inhabits" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:183).

- ↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: "...the soul of the dead wanders for a short time in a sort of purgatory, before being reincarnated either in another form on this earth, or going to some heaven or hell, as different as imagination can make them from anything experienced on earth" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:182).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "...the object of the lamaist is by the active practice of virtue and the negative abstention from sin so to improve the soul that it can eventually escape from 'the wheel of cause and

- ↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "...the object of the lamaist is by the active practice of virtue and the negative abstention from sin so to improve the soul that it can eventually escape from 'the wheel of cause and

effect' and enter into the bliss of Nirvana or non-existence" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:190).

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: "...the object of the lamaist is by the active practice of virtue and the negative abstention from sin so to improve the soul that it can eventually escape from 'the wheel of cause and effect' and enter into the bliss of Nirvana or non-existence" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:190).

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: "...the soul of the dead wanders for a short time in a sort of purgatory, before being reincarnated either in another form on this earth, or going to some heaven or hell, as different as imagination can make them from anything experienced on earth" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:182).

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: "According to lamaist theory the child in the womb dreams continuously about its previous incarnation; it thinks it is going to be born and makes up its mind to inform its parents of its future plans; but when the cord is cut most of this knowledge goes; just a little remains in the infant's dreams, but that too disappears before he has learned to talk" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:185).

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

Notes: "...it is a major sin to destroy an animal for it is possible that its soul may be that of an ex-human being..." (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:191).

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: "...the object of the lamaist is by the active practice of virtue and the negative abstention from sin so to improve the soul that it can eventually escape from 'the wheel of cause and effect' and enter into the bliss of Nirvana or non-existence" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:190).

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "Only in their death are lamas given distinguishing treatment; they are usually cremated and never buried, whereas laymen are usually buried and never cremated; both laymen and lamas may, if the horoscope indicates it, be thrown into the river" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:193).

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: "Only in their death are lamas given distinguishing treatment; they are usually cremated and never buried, whereas laymen are usually buried and never cremated..." (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:193).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

– Yes

Notes: "Only in their death are lamas given distinguishing treatment; they are usually cremated and never buried, whereas laymen are usually buried and never cremated..." (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:193).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Interment:

– No

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Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

– Yes

Notes: "Only in their death are lamas given distinguishing treatment; they are usually cremated and never buried, whereas laymen are usually buried and never cremated..." (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:193).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

Notes: "The body is put into the grave still sitting in the basket, orientated to face Kinchenjunga [the after world]; then on the top of the grave and corpse is put a big flat stone and on the top of that four cooking stones supporting another flat stone. On the top of this is placed a little white stone which serves as an indication that the place is a grave and should not be touched" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:349).

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– No

Notes: (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:349)

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

Notes: (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:349)

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

Notes: (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:349)

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No evidence for cannibalism was found among any of the ethnographic sources.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– Yes

Notes: "Young children should always be thrown into the river..." (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:346).

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1850 indicates that "secondary contact with the body or bones of the deceased does not occur" (Schroeder, 2001; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1850 indicates that "secondary contact with the body or bones of the deceased does not occur", and SCCS Variable 1851 indicates that "disarticulation does not occur or is not recoverable archaeologically" (Schroeder, 2001; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No evidence for co-sacrifices was found in any ethnographic source. Additionally, among the Lepcha Buddhists, it is a great sin to kill any animal.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Formal burials are present among laymen. For lamas, the body is burned, not buried. For a detailed description of burials, see Gorer and Hutton, 1958, pages 346-356.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "...the supernaturals are divided into three categories, mostly benevolent, neutral, and mostly malevolent. The supernaturals which are mostly benevolent are called gods, rum, those mostly malevolent devils, moong; but both [Lamas and Mun] agree that if the gods are displeased they take on a terrifying and threatening aspect, and that the best way to deal with devils is to flatter them temporarily by treating them as gods; and whether gods or devils are prayed to the ceremony always ends by begging them vehemently to go away. Whatever their chief aspects the supernaturals are potentially dangerous. The ambivalent supernaturals, such as Thyak-dum, or Hlamen Djémé (a lamaist supernatural equated with the Mun spirit), are called either moong or rum according to the personal dealings of the speaker with them at that moment" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:183). While supernaturals are clearly present and important, the Lepcha Buddhists place a greater emphasis on individual knowledge and actions, as well as rules of morality and karma-related cause-and-effect. As such, information about supernatural beings among the Lepcha is limited.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: "...lamaism, though it deals with and reveres countless hosts of supernaturals, is in a way also atheist; it contains no major God or father-figure, and also no mother-surrogate" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:189).

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "Sakya Muni, Guru Rimpuché, is an object of special love and reverence, and might be likened emotionally to Jesus Christ" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:189).

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: "The supernaturals which are mostly benevolent are called gods, rum, those mostly malevolent devils, moong; but both agree that if the gods are displeased they take on a terrifying and threatening aspect, and that the best way to deal with devils is to flatter them temporarily by treating them as gods; and whether gods or devils are prayed to the ceremony always ends by begging them vehemently to go away. Whatever their chief aspects the supernaturals are potentially dangerous" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:183).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: While supernatural beings are present and possess positive and negative emotions, the most emphasized agent of supernatural monitoring is cause-effect. "Most important of all, lamaist ethics are founded on a belief in individual destiny and a sense of sin; lamaism contains a long, explicit and detailed list of sins which can be performed by human beings, and which are visited on the evil-doer, first by feelings of remorse and secondly by punishment either in this life or in future reincarnations"

(Gorer and Hutton, 1938:182).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: "...the supernatural sanctions which punish disapproved-of actions..." (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:182).

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: See below for more details.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: "The lamaist ethic is founded on the belief of the immortality of the soul, the principle of reincarnation, and on an automatic justice which rewards individual virtue and punishes individual sin in this and future incarnations; and, as a derivative, that an individual's condition in this life is the result of his actions in previous incarnations. This determinism is modified by behaviour during each life..." (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:190).

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more details.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: "The long list of sins of which a person is capable derive from three main causes –lust, ill-will and stupidity; virtue is acquired partly from abstention from acts deriving from such sources, partly by practising their opposites (love instead of hate, freeing captive animals instead of slaying them), and chiefly by the practice of religious ritual, including mystic contemplation" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:190).

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: Gorer and Hutton, 1938:190

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "Most important of all, lamaist ethics are founded on a belief in individual destiny and a sense of sin; lamaism contains a long, explicit and detailed list of sins which can be performed by human beings, and which are visited on the evil-doer, first by feelings of remorse and secondly by punishment either in this life or in future reincarnations" (Gorer and Hutton,

1938:182).

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Most important of all, lamaist ethics are founded on a belief in individual destiny and a sense of sin; lamaism contains a long, explicit and detailed list of sins which can be performed by human beings, and which are visited on the evil-doer, first by feelings of remorse and secondly by punishment either in this life or in future reincarnations" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:182).

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

Notes: "Most important of all, lamaist ethics are founded on a belief in individual destiny and a sense of sin; lamaism contains a long, explicit and detailed list of sins which can be performed by human beings, and which are visited on the evil-doer, first by feelings of remorse and secondly by punishment either in this life or in future reincarnations" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:182).

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: "Most important of all, lamaist ethics are founded on a belief in individual destiny and a sense of sin; lamaism contains a long, explicit and detailed list of sins which can be performed by human beings, and which are visited on the evil-doer, first by feelings of remorse and secondly by punishment either in this life or in future reincarnations" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:182).

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Notes: Supernatural punishments in the afterlife, in the form of reincarnations, are more highly emphasized.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: "...the supernatural sanctions which punish disapproved-of actions are expressed as nam-toak, a year of disaster which affects the whole community" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:182).

– Yes

Notes: "Even for acts less violently disapproved of, which incur supernatural dangers, it is not the wrong-doer alone who is involved, but the whole of his family group; punishment is seen if members of a person's family die or suffer, even though the evil-doer survives himself" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:182).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more details on supernatural rewards.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: "The lamaist ethic is founded on the belief of the immortality of the soul, the principle of reincarnation, and on an automatic justice which rewards individual virtue and punishes individual sin in this and future incarnations; and, as a derivative, that an individual's condition in this life is the result of his actions in previous incarnations. This determinism is modified by behaviour during each life; and the object of the lamaist is by the active practice of virtue and the negative abstention from sin so to improve the soul that it can eventually escape from 'the wheel of cause and effect' and enter into the bliss of Nirvana or non-existence" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:190).

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: "The lamaist ethic is founded on the belief of the immortality of the soul, the principle of reincarnation, and on an automatic justice which rewards individual virtue and punishes individual sin in this and future incarnations; and, as a derivative, that an individual's condition in this life is the result of his actions in previous incarnations. This determinism is modified by behaviour during each life; and the object of the lamaist is by the active practice of virtue and the negative abstention from sin so to improve the soul that it can eventually escape from 'the wheel of cause and effect' and enter into the bliss of Nirvana or non-existence" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:190).

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– Yes

Notes: "...for the lama the soul wanders for forty-nine days in a sort of purgatory, after which it is judged and rewarded and sent on to its next incarnation, whether it be on the earth as another human being or as an animal or to heaven for a period of blessedness or to hell for a period of torment" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:346).

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– Yes

Notes: "The lamaist ethic is founded on the belief of the immortality of the soul, the

principle of reincarnation, and on an automatic justice which rewards individual virtue and punishes individual sin in this and future incarnations; and, as a derivative, that an individual's condition in this life is the result of his actions in previous incarnations. This determinism is modified by behaviour during each life; and the object of the lamaist is by the active practice of virtue and the negative abstention from sin so to improve the soul that it can eventually escape from 'the wheel of cause and effect' and enter into the bliss of Nirvana or non-existence" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:190).

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: "Most important of all, lamaist ethics are founded on a belief in individual destiny and a sense of sin; lamaism contains a long, explicit and detailed list of sins which can be performed by human beings, and which are visited on the evil-doer, first by feelings of remorse and secondly by punishment either in this life or in future reincarnations" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:182).

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: See questions below for more details.

Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Gorer and Hutton, 1938:190

Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: "The lamaist ethic is founded on the belief of the immortality of the soul, the principle of reincarnation, and on an automatic justice which rewards individual virtue and punishes individual sin in this and future incarnations; and, as a derivative, that an individual's condition in this life is the result of his actions in previous incarnations. This determinism is modified by behaviour during each life..." (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:190).

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

Virtues here are normatively-desirable, internalized habits, dispositions or behavioral ideals.

– Yes

Notes: "...the object of the lamaist is by the active practice of virtue and the negative abstention from sin so to improve the soul that it can eventually escape from 'the wheel of cause and effect' and enter into the bliss of Nirvana or non-existence" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:190).

Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

Notes: See Gorer and Hutton, 1938, page 190

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Notes: "...all that it is possible for laymen to do is to abstain from sin and support the lamas, in the hope that they will be rewarded by being themselves lamas in their next incarnations" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:190).

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

Notes: DiMaggio, 2003

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: "...Lamas are required neither to remain celibate nor to practise abstinence" (Morris, 1938:70).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No evidence for human sacrifice was found in the ethnographic sources. Further, killing even an animal is considered a sin, so human sacrifice is most likely not practiced.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No evidence for human sacrifice was found in the ethnographic sources. Further, killing even an animal is considered a sin, so human sacrifice is most likely not practiced.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No evidence for human sacrifice was found in the ethnographic sources. Further, killing even an

animal is considered a sin, so human sacrifice is most likely not practiced.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: "Lamas are meant to perform various private devotions when they wake in the night, early in the morning and in the evening" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:201).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists

– No

Notes: "But in lamaism the layman has practically no role at all; he cannot pray to, address or influence the supernaturals save through the intermediary of a lama; and therefore conversion to lamaism without admission to instruction could mean little more than a sort of voluntary tax" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:188).

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: "The lamas have to visit the monastery twice every Tibetan month; on the 10th. a festival is held in honour of Guru Rimpuché and on the 15th. in honour of Kinchenjunga. The feasts which accompany these festivals are meant to be given by a pair of householders in turn, so that from the villages of Lingthem and Panung each householder is responsible for half a communal feast every year" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:201). See Gorer and Hutton, 1938, page 203 for more details on large-scale rituals.

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Lamas attend and oversee ritual performance (see Gorer and Hutton, 1938:201-203).

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Lamas attend and oversee ritual performance (see Gorer and Hutton, 1938:201-203).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

This question refers to the wider society in which the religious group is located.

– A chiefdom

Notes: "Each Lepcha village is traditionally headed by a village leader, who is responsible for keeping order and collecting taxes" (DiMaggio, 2003). Additionally, among the Lepcha, there is one level of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is reflective of a petty chiefdom (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Young boys whose horoscopes mark them to become a Lama are provided with religious education at monasteries, where they are taught to read and write (among other lessons).

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:87, 195-196).

Is such education open to both males and females:

– No

Notes: Females are permitted to be nuns, but not Lamas. Most nuns of Lingthem had no real training and could not read or write. (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:72-77).

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Notes: "There are no shops in Lingtem, no doctor, and no school" (Morris, 1938:25).

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: "Sikkim is today an independent Native State ruled by an hereditary Maharajah; in his work he is assisted by a number of large land-owners and hereditary ministers called Kazi, and also by the advice of a resident British Political Officer" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:42).

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20 indicates that food is stored in individual houses (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20 indicates that food is stored in individual houses (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: "Land transport is done exclusively by human carriers, with at most the aid of a tumpline, a carrying pole, or the like...routes of land transport consist exclusively (or almost so) of unimproved trails or footpaths" (Murdock and Morrow, 1970). From this information, it can be assumed that transportation infrastructure is not present among the Lepcha.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: "Land transport is done exclusively by human carriers, with at most the aid of a tumpline, a carrying pole, or the like...routes of land transport consist exclusively (or almost so) of unimproved trails or footpaths" (Murdock and Morrow, 1970). From this information, it can be assumed that transportation infrastructure is not present among the Lepcha.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: No, but members of the religious group are expected to support the lamas. "The lamas (to a lesser extent the nuns) are arranged in a disciplined hierarchy. They are a section of society which performs for the whole society its religious functions; in return the rest of society should give material support to the lamas" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:192).

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, taxes are levied by the state of Sikkim (see Gorer and Hutton, 1938:123).

Enforcement

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "Police functions are specialized and institutionalized on at least some level or levels of political integration" (Tuden and Marshall, 1972).

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: "The Mandal [headman] is responsible to the Court [of the state of Sikkim] for the maintenance of good order in the village and for the collection of taxes; if there is a deficit he is liable to have to make it up. In relation to the other villagers he stands in the position of an elder relative—father or uncle or elder brother; he arranges the marriages of most of the young people, he looks after everybody's welfare and happiness, giving advice on personal or agricultural matters where they appear needed, and acting as intermediary between the villagers and the Court" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:127).

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The State of Sikkim enforces punishment, which the Lepcha are subject to (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:42)

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: "Nowadays religious instruction is given in Tibetan. In Zongu literacy is exclusively confined to the reading of Tibetan scriptures and has no sort of influence or use in everyday life; lamas who can read religious books and write religious formulas are quite incapable of reading or writing a letter in any language" (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:39).

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Tibetan (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:39, 211).

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Although Tibetan is available, most laymen neither read nor write (Gorer and Hutton, 1938:39, 211).

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The society, of which the religious group is a part of, provides food for themselves. The Lepchas are primarily agriculturalists, "practicing intensive agriculture on permanent fields, utilizing fertilization by compost or animal manure, crop rotation, or other techniques so that fallowing is either unnecessary or is confined to relatively short periods." Animal husbandry provides an additional source of subsistence, and hunting makes a supplemental contribution to food supply. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Hunting (including marine animals)
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The society, of which the religious group is a part of, provides food for themselves. The Lepchas are primarily agriculturalists, "practicing intensive agriculture on permanent fields, utilizing fertilization by compost or animal manure, crop rotation, or other techniques so that fallowing is either unnecessary or is confined to relatively short periods." Animal husbandry provides an additional source of subsistence, and hunting makes a supplemental contribution to food supply. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.